

Classifying Environmental Stimuli Using Electrical Signals from Hedera Plants

Sebastian Mai

sebastian.mai@uni-konstanz.de

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Cyber-Physical Systems Group

Department of Computer and Information Science, University of Konstanz

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Abstract

Plants have the ability to quickly react and adapt to changes in their environment. Based on the experienced conditions, they will adjust their internal electric potential. This adjustment is executed quickly and can be measured using electrodes. As [Buss et al. \[2023\]](#) describe, we will look at the plant as a black box and will only focus on the phytosensing approach. Phytosensing is trying to interpret the plants' signals in order to gain information of the environmental conditions. Our research is focused on building a robust and accurate classification for the plant Hedera. With the designed experiments we can measure electric potential of plants under multiple different environmental conditions called stimuli. In our approach, we extract statistical features and use statistical discriminant analysis methods for the classification. The classification is either based on a single stimulus or multiple stimuli, respectively. Results have shown that it is in fact possible to build an accurate classification method for single stimuli. When looking at the results for the classification across multiple stimuli using up to nine classes, proves yet challenging and needs further refinement.

1 Introduction

Plants change their internal electric potential in response to external stimuli the plant experiences. These changes can be measured and thereafter analysed and interpreted. This approach, called phytosensing is using plants as sensors by interpreting the produced signal ([Buss et al. \[2023\]](#)). The collected data can be used in many different ways and can provide a solution to a variety of problems. It could be beneficial in the agriculture sector, where farmers could react to the need of the plants in a more suitable way. For example, by watering only certain areas or applying pesticides in specific target regions, which potentially could save money as well as time in the long run. Within cities, plants could be used to monitor environmental factors by measuring their electric potential as proposed by the WatchPlant project ([Hamann et al. \[2021\]](#)). Therefore, plants can be an inexpensive space saving solution in cities to gather data, compared to expensive

sensors and other data collection and processing hardware. However, in order to convert electric potential into a meaningful prediction, a classification method is needed. Our main focus in this paper is to build a robust classification method. In our research we conduct experiments over a three week time span with a total of four different stimuli. These stimuli are red and blue light, heat and wind. For each the electrical potential is measured. Those datasets are then preprocessed. Based on that preprocessed data, we extract statistical features. These include basic ones like mean and variance but also more complex ones like the Hjorth parameters and wavelet packet entropy. Each resulting dataset for one stimulus consists of three classes that we classify using linear discriminant analysis, k-nearest neighbor and Adaboost as classification algorithms.

2 Related Work

In recent years development of techniques to measure electric potential in plants have progressed using different ways to measure the potential, as well as using different type of plants and setups. However, some of the earliest findings date back to 1783 where, according to Volkov [2006], Berthelon first described electric signals in plants, which was later picked up by Darwin (1875) and Burdon-Sanderson (1873). Burdon-Sanderson was the first known to record the action potential (AP) of plants, namely in the leaves of the Venus flytrap (*Dionaea muscipula*). Recently, new techniques to measure and use the data have emerged. According to Li et al. [2021] there has been remarkable progress in this field. They claim, that research on the electrical potential of plants encompasses a wide variety of disciplines and different methodologies and therefore is interesting for a broader range of researchers. However, only measuring the potential is insufficient since it is hard to interpret the raw signal. Therefore, multiple approaches explored classification methods based on the measured change in potential. Chatterjee et al. [2015] are collecting data of the plants' electrical responses based on different stimuli and calculate statistical features, in combination with different classifiers. Their plant of choice is the tomato plant. As stimuli they add sodium chloride (NaCl) using 5 and 10 ml with a concentration of 3 mol, sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4) using 5 ml with a concentration of 0.05 mol or ozone (O_3) with a concentration of 16 ppm. The experimental setup features a Faraday cage to avoid external interference of the measurements. In total, they calculate 11 statistical features and use five different classification variants including linear and quadratic discriminant analysis and apply naive Bayes with linear and quadratic kernel in combination with the diagonal estimate of the covariance. In addition, they also use the Mahalanobis classifier. They achieve an average accuracy of over 63 % using their best feature sets. The Mahalanobis classifier performs worst of the five tested classifiers. It has the lowest average accuracy for the individual features but also for the best performing feature set. Buss et al. [2023] follow a similar approach. They also use tomato plants as well as *Zamioculcas zamiifolia*. Instead of damaging stimuli, the authors apply red and blue light as well as wind and heat. They measure the potential but also the impedance. From there they calculate statistical features and use those features as input for discriminant analysis classifiers.

In addition, they use deep learning methods. By using different classifiers such as MLP, t-LeNet or ResNet among others they achieve accuracies in between 57 % and 89 % for two classes, 53 % to 91 % for three classes and 43 % to 83 % for five classes.

3 Experiments

3.1 Setup

For every experiment we use exactly one plant. The plant of choice here is as already mentioned in Sec. 1, the Hedera, commonly known as Ivy. To conduct the experiments we use a laboratory setup. As described by [Buss et al. \[2023\]](#), this means that the plants will grow in non-greenhouse conditions with minimal care. Every three to four days the plants are watered. If a plant is not used for an experiment it is placed outside and experiences normal temperature changes as well as wind and partial rain influence. One plant is used on three to four consecutive days for experiments, before a different plant is used. This procedure allows for good data extraction where constant healing processes within the plant, after insertion of the electrodes, are present. We use a total of four sensors for each experiment. All of the sensors use electrodes to measure the potential. Due to very small voltage of those potentials, it is crucial to isolate the setup from outside electromagnetic disturbances. Therefore, a box which is approximately 158x83x79 cm in size is used. Three sides of the box including the door and the top are transparent in order to allow the light to shine through. The fourth wall and the bottom are made of a material impermeable by light. Around the box is a thin metal layer of mesh creating the Faraday cage. The cage is grounded using a metal clip (attached to the metal mesh) with a wire going into the ground wire of a power outlet. The entire setup is mounted on four wheels, that allow for easy transportation. The plant, together with the four sensors are placed into the box/cage. We use three PhytoNode (PN) sensors by [Buss et al. \[2022\]](#) and one CYBRES sensor by [Kernbach \[2022\]](#). Two PhytoNodes are used to measure the electrical potential of the plant, while the third one is used to control the measurement and detect any electromagnetic disturbances. Each node has two electrodes that are grounded. Electrodes are according to [Buss et al. \[2022\]](#) silver coated copper wires. These electrodes are inserted into the plant with a distance of approximately 15 cm. One of the two PhytoNodes connected to the plant measures the electrical potential from stem to stem and the other one measures the electrical potential from leaf to stem. The CYBRES sensor can measure the electrical impedance and the electrical potential, each having two channels (1 channel = 2 electrodes). We only use the electrical potential measurement. The two electrodes are inserted in the same way as for the PhytoNode. One channel measures stem to stem the other measures stem to leaf. On top of that the CYBRES sensor can measure other things such as external temperature and light levels or the transpiration. The transpiration is measured by clipping a sensor clip to one of the plants' leaves. The setup can be seen in Fig. 1. All four sensors are connected via a micro-USB cable to a Raspberry Pi 4. The Pi is used to collect the sensed data at a central point, from which it can be transferred to a device, that is more capable of doing the workload for processing and classification tasks. The Pi also controls the

Figure 1: Plant with attached sensors in the box with open door

stimuli by activating a Wi-Fi socket at specific times. The Wi-Fi socket used is the TPlink HS100. All stimuli generating devices are plugged into this socket. This micro computer is located outside the Faraday cage. During the testing phase we could not find any evidence, that the Pi influences the measurements when it is inside the cage. However, due to the nature of a Faraday cage, it is hard for the Pi to control the Wi-Fi socket via a Wi-Fi connection. In addition, transferring data from the Pi to the laptop is difficult due to the low signal strength caused by the Faraday cage.

3.2 Experimental Workflow

Before we start with the experiments for the different stimuli, we need to make sure that our measurements are not distorted by outside disturbances. Therefore, we conduct one control experiment for each type of stimuli generator. So, in total we conducted three control experiments. One control experiment lasts 20 min encompassing a 5 min prestimulus phase, a 10 min application phase and a 5 min poststimulus phase. In the stimulus phase we switch the stimuli generators on, without the plant experiencing the stimuli. For example, for the light stimuli, the plant within the Faraday cage was put into a box allowing no light to shine through. Then in the stimuli phase the light is switched on. If the potential of the plant changes drastically we can infer that the measurement is distorted. The experiments for creating the final datasets follow the same procedure that was proposed by Buss et al. [2023] and have a total duration of 130 min. There is a 60 min prestimulus phase, where there is ideally no influ-

ence on the plant followed by a 10 min long stimulus phase, where one of the stimuli described in Sec. 3.3 is applied. In this time there should be a change in potential and transpiration. After the 10 min stimuli application there is a 60 min long post stimulus phase where again no stimuli is applied. In this phase the potential ideally goes back to the normal or base state of the prestimulus phase. Directly after one experiment is finished the next one will be started. In total six experiments a day are conducted.

3.3 Stimuli

As explained in Sec. 2 there are different types of stimuli that can be applied to plants. However, we focus on applying red and blue light, wind and heat. At the start of the project, we had the idea of having more damaging stimuli. However, the small duration for the project as well as the limited availability of Hedera plants force us to focus on the four mentioned stimuli. All stimuli are applied from outside the Faraday cage in order to not interfere with the measurements. After testing each stimulus first, application and data collection for each stimulus is done as mentioned in Sec. 3.2. For the light stimuli grow lights are used (see Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Example of the two different panel types. In an experiment only one color is switched on at the same time

The panels for red lights have more LED's and we therefore only use five panels consisting of approximately 165 LED's. For the blue light stimuli we use six panels consisting of approximately 60 LED's. The panel configuration is depicted in Table 1.

panel	left side	front	right side	top
red light	2	1	1	1
blue light	1	2	1	2

Table 1: Configuration of the panels for red and blue light

The heat stimulus is produced by a conventional heater (Rowenta SO2320F0 Instant Comfort Compact) element which is placed at the back side of the box with a distance of approximately 24 cm. The heater and the box are connected with a pipe with ≈ 9.5 cm wide pipe ensuring a constant flow of heated air from the heater into the box. When heating we have a temperature boundary, which is dependent on the starting temperature. We want to heat the cage up by 5°C additional to the starting temperature and then keep a constant temperature.

Figure 3: Left: Heater setup mounted to the cage, Right: Rowenta SO2320F0 Instant Comfort Compact with the attached pipe

The fourth stimulus we apply is wind. We use the same opening in the box as for the heat stimulus, however we mount the fan directly to the box/cage. We use the EBM Papst 4414 HH axial fan. This fan is constantly powered by 24 V/DC allowing up to 5000 rpm. The volume flow is $280 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$ with a dynamic pressure of 208 Pa according to Papst [2019]. This results in enough air movement to measure the changes in the potential.

Figure 4: Left: Fan mounted to the box/cage, Right: EBM Papst 4414 HH axial fan

4 Data Processing

4.1 Preprocessing

The raw data itself is not really suited to directly extract statistical features. There are outliers and noise that we first need to get rid of or at least reduce. Therefore, we implement a pipeline, that allows us to bring the data in a format that can then be further used for the feature extraction described in Sec. 4.2. We use the following preprocessing steps:

1. Load file
2. Split into experiments
3. For each experiment:
 - (a) Calculate mean of 60 min prestimuli interval
 - (b) Perform background subtraction for the interval (20 min prestimuli, 10 min stimuli and 20 min poststimuli) using the calculated mean of the complete 60 min prestimuli interval
 - (c) Perform Fast-Fourier-Transformation on the interval
 - (d) Remove unnecessary frequencies
 - (e) Transform the interval back into the time domain
 - (f) Cut to correct and equal interval lengths (10 min prestimuli, 10 min stimuli and 10 min stimuli)

We will only elaborate on 3a to 3f since 1 and 2 are trivial. As shown above we calculate the mean of entire prestimuli period. This mean is then used to perform the background subtraction, since we are not interested in the actual

values of the electric potential but rather the change of the potential. We perform the background subtraction only on the interval used for the classification and not the complete dataset (more in Sec. 4.3). After the background subtraction, we perform the Fast-Fourier-Transformation (FFT) to transform our signal from the time domain into the frequency domain. However, due to some issues with the numpy library we increase the interval size of the pre- and post-stimuli and cut it to the correct size later on. The problems in the calculation are caused by the fact that our signal is not periodic. The FFT is according to [Heideman et al. \[1984\]](#) a well known and efficient algorithm that can calculate the Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) of a signal. They also state, that the DFT is essentially a frequency representation of the signal thus answering the question: What frequencies is a signal composed of?

After the calculation of the FFT we remove higher frequencies to smooth out the signal as seen in Fig. 5.

Figure 5: CYBRES stem-stem measurement for heat after removing unwanted frequencies

Then we calculate the inverse FFT to transform the signal back into the time domain and as mentioned cut it to the correct size (30 min interval in total) as seen in Fig. 6. The plot is split into the three consecutive sections (prestimuli, stimuli and poststimuli). Compared to the original signal, the transformed signal is smoothed.

Figure 6: CYBRES stem-stem (CH1) and leaf-stem (CH2) original signal and signal after the inverse transformation.

4.2 Feature Extraction

After the preprocessing the data is in the correct format and length to be analysed. As mentioned earlier, for the calculation of features each experiment is split into the three sections, each 10 minutes long. The following features are calculated for each interval separately.

We extract common features used in the analysis of electric potentials in plants and humans such as: mean (μ), variance (σ^2), skewness (γ), kurtosis (β), interquartile range (IQR), Hjorth mobility (HM) and complexity (HC), wavelet packet entropy (WPE) and average spectral power (ASP). These are the same features Buss et al. [2023] used which is a subset of the features used by Chatterjee et al. [2015]. To calculate the features we use different python libraries such as tsfel, numpy, scipy and antropy (Barandas et al. [2020], Harris et al. [2020], Virtanen et al. [2020] and Vallant [2018]) as well as our own implementation for WPE and ASP in combination with the mentioned libraries. Calculation of mean, variance, skewness and kurtosis can be described with following equations where x_i represents the samples and n the number of total samples.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mu &= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \\
 \sigma^2 &= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \mu)^2 \\
 \gamma &= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{x_i - \mu}{\sigma} \right)^3 \\
 \beta &= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{x_i - \mu}{\sigma} \right)^4
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

The interquartile range is, according to [Upton and Cook \[1996\]](#) defined as the difference between the upper quartile Q_3 and lower quartile Q_1 , This equates to the 75th and the 25th percentile of the data respectively ([Dekking et al.](#)).

$$IQR = Q_3 - Q_1 \quad (2)$$

Hjorth parameters by [Hjorth \[1970\]](#) are more commonly used in Electroencephalography. There are three parameters, namely activity, mobility and complexity. We extract only mobility and complexity. Mobility uses the variance σ_1^2 , and its derivative σ_2^2 . Complexity uses the same but adds the second derivative of the signal σ_3^2 . For our calculations we used the formula proposed by [Hjorth \[1970\]](#) and implemented by [Vallant \[2018\]](#):

$$\begin{aligned} HM &= \sqrt{\frac{\sigma_2^2}{\sigma_1^2}} \\ HC &= \frac{\sqrt{\frac{\sigma_3^2}{\sigma_2^2}}}{\sqrt{\frac{\sigma_2^2}{\sigma_1^2}}} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The wavelet packet entropy (WPE) has become a well-known tool for signal processing applications ([Rioul and Duhamel \[1992\]](#)). According to [Buss et al. \[2023\]](#) wavelets are “decaying wave like oscillations with zero mean”. Depending on the window size, we have different resolutions in the high and low frequencies ([Ocak \[2009\]](#)). They furthermore state, that there are two main types of wavelet transforms, namely continuous and discrete transforms. The latter being more computationally efficient. The discrete wavelet by [Brunton and Kutz \[2022\]](#) is defined as:

$$\mathcal{W}_\psi(f)(j, k) = \langle f, \psi_{j,k} \rangle \quad (4)$$

$\psi(t)$ is the mother wavelet and $\psi_{j,k}$ represents the wavelet family and can be defined as:

$$\psi_{j,k} = \frac{1}{a^j} \psi\left(\frac{t - kb}{a^j}\right) \quad (5)$$

As a mother wavelet we use the same as [Buss et al. \[2023\]](#), namely the Daubechies 1 mother wavelet. Furthermore [Brunton and Kutz \[2022\]](#) states that a is used for scaling and b for the translation of ψ . Once we calculate all the coefficients $\mathcal{W}_\psi(f)(j, k)$ we can calculate the wavelet packet entropy.

$$WPE = - \sum \mathcal{W}^2 \log(\mathcal{W}^2) \quad (6)$$

The average spectral power (ASP) can be described as the sum over the power spectral density (PSD). We follow the same approach and calculation as [Buss et al. \[2023\]](#) using the already implemented library `scipy` ([Virtanen et al. \[2020\]](#)).

We segment the data into k overlapping segments and apply a Hann window to each of them. Each of those windows will be transformed using the Fast-Fourier-Transformation. The results are k periodograms that are averaged. The resulting function is,

$$ASP = \sum_{f \in F} \text{PSD}(f) \quad (7)$$

where F equates to all the frequencies in the signal.

All features for one stimuli are normalized for each interval for all experiments (pre/stim/post) using normal min-max normalization.

4.3 Classification

Once the features are calculated we start the classification task. Each stimulus dataset consists of three classes. These classes are prestimuli, stimuli and poststimuli. In each dataset each column represents the calculated features and the last column equates to the class of the data point. In total, each stimuli is classified using the three following algorithms: Linear discriminant analysis (LDA), K-nearest neighbor (KNN) and Adaboost (ADA). For this we use the python library sklearn (Pedregosa et al. [2011]). LDA is a data analysis algorithm first proposed by R. Fisher in order to discriminate between different species of flowers (Xanthopoulos et al. [2013]). LDA is trying to find a linear combination of features so that multiple classes can be separated (Brunton and Kutz [2022]). This assumes that the data is Gaussian distributed (Buss et al. [2023]). The main idea behind KNN is that an incoming data point is classified based on the majority class of the surrounding neighbors whereby the parameter k is representing the number of neighbors the algorithm takes into consideration. We opted for $k = 3$. Unlike LDA, KNN is able to have non-linear decision boundaries. In addition, KNN is the only lazy learning algorithm. Adaboost is a less known algorithm. Broadly speaking it is a form of the random forest algorithm which takes an ensemble of decision tree models into account. It starts off with initializing equal weights for all training data and boosts data based on how hard it is to classify, shifting its focus to data points that are not as easy to classify (Brunton and Kutz [2022]). In example, adaboost will initialize a classifier with some initial weights. We then classify all training data on that classifier. If a data point is incorrectly classified, it will be boosted compared to a correctly classified data point. Using these new weights, a new classifier will be built. After building a certain amount of classifiers the best model is selected (Hastie et al. [2009]). However, in order to use the classifier we need to first choose our features upon which we want to classify. We use two different approaches, Sequential Forward Selection (SFS), and Sequential Backward Selection (SBS). The main difference between these approaches is that SFS starts with an empty set and selects the best performing feature for each iteration, while SBS starts with a full set removing the least performing. SFS was already used in previous approaches such as the one by Buss et al. [2023]. We want to see whether or not there is a difference in accuracy between the two approaches.

5 Results

In this section we will look at the measurements and the classification results. We try to classify the data in different ways. We start the classification using three classes (prestimuli, stimuli and poststimuli) itself and later combining that with different sensor data (CYBRES stem-stem, CYBRES leaf-stem, PN stem-stem, PN leaf-stem). Additionally, we also look at the classification accuracies between multiple stimuli. This adds more complexity since we add more classes for the classifier to correctly identify. For each classification run we compute the accuracy of the classification and generate a corresponding confusion matrix. In addition, when two features in total are selected we plot the dataset with the corresponding decision boundaries. Here we will present our best results with selected plots and tables. The total number of results with all tables of accuracies can be found in Sec. [Appendix](#). All plots as well as the link to the Github repository with the code can be found as supplementary material ([Mai \[2024\]](#)).

5.1 Measurements

We measure the potential for each stimuli with a total of four measurements in each experiment. The sampling rate for the PhytoNodes is about 300 Hz while the CYBRES sensor samples at 0.1 Hz for the blue and red stimuli and at 1 Hz for heat and wind stimuli. Here we will show some example results, since our main objective was the classification. However, in order to understand the classification result it is necessary to look at the measurements. In general, we observed that the light stimuli had better reactions (changes in potential) compared to the heat and wind stimuli (see [Fig. 7](#) and [8](#)).

Figure 7: Example CYBRES measurement for the red stimuli with the two measurements (stem-stem/CH1 and leaf-stem/CH2), transpiration and light intensity

Comparing the light stimuli blue had less impact on the plant compared to red. This can be due to the plants physiological nature but also that a higher light intensity would be needed for the blue stimuli. The sensors have difficulties to get a reliable and relevant measurement of the potential for heat and wind stimuli. Fig. 8 shows that for the heat stimuli we only observe a distinct change in the transpiration. The potential changes are rather random and did not show a distinct change during the stimuli application. One of the reasons could be that the heater element we use is not powerful enough.

As mentioned in Sec. 3.3 the heater is supposed to heat the cage by 5°C and keep the temperature constant. However, we never reach the $+5^{\circ}\text{C}$ barrier. We

are only able to heat up the cage by about 3°C. The wind stimuli under performs as well, with no distinctive response in the potential. Multiple reasons could be the explanation for this behavior. Either the used fan is too weak or the plant is too far away from the wind source. For both, heat and wind, there is the chance that the Hedera plant might just in general not change their potential in a relevant manner. However, further experiments would have to be conducted in order to prove this relation.

Figure 8: Example CYBRES measurement for the heat stimuli with the two measurements (stem-stem/CH1 and leaf-stem/CH2), transpiration and temperature

5.2 Single Stimulus

In the single stimuli the amount of classes stay the same during all classification runs. We have a total of three classes (prestimuli, stimuli and poststimuli). In the following parts we refer to CYBRES stem-stem as CH1, CYBRES leaf-stem as CH2, PN stem-stem as P9 and PN leaf-stem as P5. We test CH1, CH2, P9 and P5 in various combinations. We test each of them individually using both, SFS and SBS and all stimuli. The best single channel accuracy is achieved for the red stimuli using LDA. We achieve a maximal accuracy of 96 % for both SFS and SBS. Both feature selection methods select the same features, namely $[\mu, \sigma^2, \gamma, \text{IQR}, \text{WPE}, \text{ASP}]$. Fig. 9 shows the respective results.

(a) Decision boundaries with entire data set plotted (b) Confusion matrix for the max accuracy of the test data

Figure 9: Decision boundaries and confusion matrix for red stimuli for LDA using SFS for CH2

Interestingly, looking at a single stimulus, always one outperforms the other channels. This behavior is random and changed when looking at different stimuli. For the blue stimuli CH1 performs best with a maximum accuracy of 95 % using SFS or SBS in combination with LDA and KNN. ADA achieves the same accuracy, however only if SBS is used. P9 is the worst performing channel for the blue stimuli with a minimal accuracy of 25 % using ADA and SBS. In contrast, looking at the wind stimuli we observe that P9 achieves the highest accuracy, with a value of 84 % using LDA with SFS, KNN with SFS or SBS or ADA using SFS, whereas CH1 is the worst performing channel achieving only a minimal accuracy of 47 % using KNN and SFS (Fig. 10). The detailed selection of features is listed in Sec. [Single Stimulus](#) in the appendix.

Figure 10: Max accuracies for single channel and one stimuli

The overall best performing stimulus for single channel measurements is the red stimuli achieving a total average accuracy of 77 % over all classifier and feature selection methods. After testing and classifying each channel on their own we combine them. To understand how accuracies differ within the same sensor type we test the combinations CH1 and CH2 together and P5 and P9 together. In addition, we also test the combinations CH1 and P9 as well as CH2 and P5 to get classification results for different sensor types but “identical” measurement types, both stem-stem or leaf-stem. The result shows a decrease in accuracies compared to the best performing single channel classification. With accuracies of 84 % the best results are achieved for the stimuli wind or red light. For the wind stimuli KNN in combination with SBS and for the red stimuli KNN in combination with either SFS or SBS is used. Wind uses the CH2 with P5 combination whereas red performs best with the CH1 and CH2 combination (Fig. 11).

(a) Decision boundaries with entire data set plotted

(b) Confusion matrix for the max accuracy of the test data

(c) Decision boundaries with entire data set plotted

(d) Confusion matrix for the max accuracy of the test data

Figure 11: Decision boundaries and confusion matrices for wind stimuli for KNN using SBS for CH2 and P5 above and red stimuli for KNN using SBS for CH1 and CH2 below

The red stimuli uses less features for achieving similar accuracies. Red selects a total of 2 features being $[\mu, WPE]$, whereas wind selects a total of 7 features being $[\mu, \gamma, \beta, IQR, WPE, HM, ASP]$.

Compared to looking at a single channel we can not see a clear accuracy improvement when looking at varying combinations of either staying within one sensor type but using different physiological measurements or having two different sensor types but using the same physiological measurement (see Fig. 12)

Figure 12: Accuracies for all tested channel combinations for all stimuli

In the appendix one can find the selected features. Lastly, we combine all channels together. Again by using the dataset for the red stimuli, we achieve the best accuracy with a value of 70 % using KNN with SFS (see Fig. 13).

Figure 13: Accuracies for all stimuli using all channels

Fig. 14 depicts the decision boundaries as well as the confusion matrix for the best combination.

(a) Decision boundaries with entire data set plotted (b) Confusion matrix for the max accuracy of the test data

Figure 14: Decision boundaries and confusion matrix for red stimuli for LDA using SFS for all channels combined

In general, we see an overall decrease in accuracies when using all channels at the same time compared to just using only two channels at one time.

In order to calculate the result of various combinations of channels we concatenate the datasets. However, by doing so, the feature space stays the same (9 features). Therefore, only the amount of available data points (rows) increases. For us it is important to also test combinations, where we increase the feature space. For this purpose we do not just concatenate the datasets, but rather interleave the columns of two channels, resulting in a feature space that is twice as big (18 features). When a feature is from a stem-stem measurement an “_s” is added to the name, for a leaf-stem measurement a “_b” is added. We test the combination CH1 with CH2, P5 with P9 and then all together. When looking at the two channel configurations the best performing stimuli is the blue light with an accuracy of 100 % with CH1 and CH2 with LDA and SBS. For all 4 channels combined it is the wind stimulus achieving 82 % while utilising KNN with SBS. The selected features here are $[\mu_s, \mu_b, \sigma_s^2, \beta_s, \beta_b, \text{IQR}_s, \text{IQR}_b, \text{WPE}_s, \text{WPE}_b, \text{HM}_s, \text{HM}_b, \text{HC}_s, \text{ASP}_s]$ and $[\mu_s, \mu_b, \sigma_b^2, \gamma_s, \gamma_b, \beta_s, \beta_b, \text{IQR}_s, \text{IQR}_b, \text{WPE}_s, \text{WPE}_b, \text{HM}_s, \text{HM}_b, \text{HC}_b, \text{ASP}_s, \text{ASP}_b]$ respectively. Corresponding plots for the decision boundaries and confusion matrices can be seen in Fig. 15.

(a) Decision boundaries with entire data set plotted

(b) Confusion matrix for the max accuracy of the test data

(c) Decision boundaries with entire data set plotted

(d) Confusion matrix for the max accuracy of the test data

Figure 15: Decision boundaries and confusion matrices for blue stimuli for LDA using SBS for CH1 and CH2 above and wind stimuli for KNN using SBS for all four channels below

We notice that an increase of the feature space, not only increases our maximal accuracy but also improved the accuracies throughout all stimuli and classifiers compared to the two and four channel configurations with the feature space of length 9 (see Fig.12, 13, 16). Due to this we decided to continue with the increased feature space in order to classify multiple stimuli at once.

Figure 16: Accuracies for all stimuli using the increased feature space with three different channel configurations (CH1 and CH2, P5 and P9, all four channels together)

5.3 Multiple Stimuli

Due to the short time of the project we could not test all combinations of using more than one stimulus. We only test these three combinations: CH1 and CH2, P5 and P9 and then all stimuli together using a features space with 18 features that are selected using either SFS or SBS. For stimuli, we test the combinations blue and red, blue, red and heat and last all four stimuli together. We assume, that the prestimuli class is the same for all stimuli, as during this period of the experiments no environmental changes are applied. Stimuli and poststimuli are separate classes for each stimuli because responses differ depending on the stimuli. When combining multiple stimuli we need to make sure that all classes are somewhat equally distributed. Therefore, if we just combine the complete datasets of two or more stimuli we would obtain a shifted distribution, where the prestimuli class would be over represented. With this in mind we create two extra data sets. One for prestimuli only using CH1 and CH2 and one only using P5 and P9. When testing the all channel configuration those two sets are joined to one. Therefore, the classification is done on 5, 7 and 9 classes, respectively. Looking at the all three scenarios we notice, that only the CH1, CH2 or P5, P9 combinations outperform the all channel configuration. The max accuracy for blue, red stimuli is 75 % in the CH1, CH2 configuration using KNN with either SFS or SBS. The average accuracy is 65 % encompassing the three different channel configurations being CH1 together with CH2, P5 together with P9 and all channels joined together. For the stimuli combination blue, red and heat the

max and average accuracy decreases to 67 % with LDA using SBS for CH1, CH2 configuration and 56 % respectively. The lowest accuracies are achieved using all four stimuli with a max accuracy of 63 % using the P5, P9 configuration with LDA in either SFS or SBS. In addition the average drops another 5 % to 51 %. These results show a clear trend, with a decrease in accuracy the more classes there are. This holds true for both max and average accuracies as seen in Fig. 17

Figure 17: Maximum accuracies for three different classifiers using both SFS and SBS for three different stimuli combinations

We also observe that in order to achieve similar accuracies with the LDA and ADA algorithms more features are needed compared to KNN (Sec. 6). In Fig. 18 we can see the confusion matrices for the best performing classifier when looking at all channels. This allows us to gain information about which classes are correctly predicted and for which the classifier struggled with. When applying only the blue and red stimuli we can see in Fig. 18a that most of the classes are correctly predicted, with only the prestimuli class showing the least good performance. For the combination of blue, red and heat stimuli the best performing classes are stimuli blue, stimuli red, and poststimuli red (Fig. 18b). Stimuli heat performs worse, however outperforms prestimuli, poststimuli blue and heat. Looking at the combination of all stimuli, as seen in Fig. 18c, we conclude, that stimuli red and poststimuli red perform best followed by stimuli blue.

(a) Blue and Red stimuli using LDA and SBS

(b) Blue, Red and Heat stimuli using KNN and SFS

(c) Blue, Red, Heat and Wind stimuli using KNN and SBS

Figure 18: Confusion Matrices for the best performing classifier when looking at all channels

Due to a lack of other combinations we can only speculate why red outperforms the other stimuli. One reason could be of course that the collected data of the other stimuli is not as “good”, meaning that the reaction of the plant and the corresponding change in potential is not big enough, for example due to a lack of strength for the blue light or too little change in temperature for the heat stimulus. More combinations and experiments need to be conducted in order to find a clear correlation.

6 Conclusion

In this work we used electrodes to measure plant potential in response to environmental stimuli. With a variety of different stimuli and analysis combinations we were able to develop a computational classification method. While some stimuli showed good responses in the electric potential, others such as heat and wind, did not. This allows for further research by either using other stimuli generators, or by improving our measuring methods. Another possibility would be to test other stimuli or to use multiple stimuli and different combinations thereof at the same time and use the resulting data for the classification. In addition, the preprocessing process could be altered. This could encompass to

add more and new methods or to simplify the process by omitting some of the implemented preprocessing steps. It could also include changing the cutoff frequencies for the FFT. Overall this could lead to better classification results. In general our results show that the Hedera plant is suitable for the development of a classification method. However, accuracies can still be improved, especially when looking at the multiple stimuli classification. Using other combinations such as classification with multiple stimuli but a small feature space might be of interest here. In addition testing other more advanced classification algorithms could be a way to go in the future as well.

References

- Marília Barandas, Duarte Folgado, Letícia Fernandes, Sara Santos, Mariana Abreu, Patrícia Bota, Hui Liu, Tanja Schultz, and Hugo Gamboa. Tsfel: Time series feature extraction library. *SoftwareX*, 11:100456, 2020. ISSN 2352-7110. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.softx.2020.100456>. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2352711020300017>.
- Steven L. Brunton and J. Nathan Kutz. *Data-Driven Science and Engineering: Machine Learning, Dynamical Systems, and Control*. Cambridge University Press, 2 edition, 2022.
- Eduard Buss, Tim-Lucas Rabbel, Viktor Horvat, Marko Krizmancic, Stjepan Bogdan, Mostafa Wahby, and Heiko Hamann. Phytonodes for environmental monitoring: Stimulus classification based on natural plant signals in an interactive energy-efficient bio-hybrid system. GoodIT '22, page 258–264, New York, NY, USA, 2022. Association for Computing Machinery. ISBN 9781450392846. doi: 10.1145/3524458.3547266.
- Eduard Buss, Till Aust, Mostafa Wahby, Tim-Lucas Rabbel, Serge Kernbach, and Heiko Hamann. Stimulus classification with electrical potential and impedance of living plants: comparing discriminant analysis and deep-learning methods. *Bioinspiration & Biomimetics*, 18(2):025003, mar 2023. doi: 10.1088/1748-3190/acbad2.
- Shre Kumar Chatterjee, Saptarshi Das, Koushik Maharatna, Elisa Masi, Luisa Santopolo, Stefano Mancuso, and Andrea Vitaletti. Exploring strategies for classification of external stimuli using statistical features of the plant electrical response. *Journal of the Royal Society Interface*, 12(104):20141225, 2015. doi: 10.1098/rsif.2014.1225.
- Frederik Michel Dekking, Cornelis Kraaikamp, Hendrik Paul Lopuhaä, and Ludolf Erwin Meester. *A Modern Introduction to Probability and Statistics: Understanding why and how*, volume 488. Springer.
- Heiko Hamann, Stjepan Bogdan, Antonio Diaz-Espejo, Laura García-Carmona, Virginia Hernandez-Santana, Serge Kernbach, Andreas Kernbach, Alfredo Quijano-López, Babak Salamat, and Mostafa Wahby. WatchPlant: Networked Bio-hybrid Systems for Pollution Monitoring of Urban Areas. volume ALIFE 2021: The 2021 Conference on Artificial Life of *ALIFE 2023: Ghost in the Machine: Proceedings of the 2023 Artificial Life Conference*, page 37, 07 2021. doi: 10.1162/isal.a.00377.
- Charles R. Harris, K. Jarrod Millman, Stéfan J. van der Walt, Ralf Gommers, Pauli Virtanen, David Cournapeau, Eric Wieser, Julian Taylor, Sebastian Berg, Nathaniel J. Smith, Robert Kern, Matti Picus, Stephan Hoyer, Marten H. van Kerkwijk, Matthew Brett, Allan Haldane, Jaime Fernández del Río, Mark Wiebe, Pearu Peterson, Pierre Gérard-Marchant, Kevin Sheppard, Tyler Reddy, Warren Weckesser, Hameer Abbasi, Christoph Gohlke, and Travis E. Oliphant. Array programming with NumPy. *Nature*, 585(7825):357–362, sep 2020. doi: 10.1038/s41586-020-2649-2. URL <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2649-2>.
- Trevor Hastie, Saharon Rosset, Ji Zhu, and Hui Zou. Multi-class adaboost. *Statistics and its Interface*, 2(3):349–360, 2009. doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.4310/SII.2009.v2.n3.a8>.
- M. Heideman, D. Johnson, and C. Burrus. Gauss and the history of the fast fourier transform. *IEEE ASSP Magazine*, 1(4):14–21, 1984. doi: 10.1109/MASSP.1984.1162257.

- Bo Hjorth. Eeg analysis based on time domain properties. *Electroencephalography and Clinical Neurophysiology*, 29(3):306–310, 1970. ISSN 0013-4694. doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0013-4694\(70\)90143-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0013-4694(70)90143-4).
- Serge Kernbach. *CYBRES Differential Impedance Spectrometer for electrochemical and electrophysiological analysis of fluids and organic tissues. Handbook and User manual*. 05 2022.
- Jin-Hai Li, Li-Feng Fan, Dong-Jie Zhao, Qiao Zhou, Jie-Peng Yao, Zhong-Yi Wang, and Lan Huang. Plant electrical signals: A multidisciplinary challenge. *Journal of Plant Physiology*, 261:153418, 2021. ISSN 0176-1617. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jplph.2021.153418>.
- Sebastian Mai. Supplementary files for the bachelor project, 03 2024. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10875918>.
- Hasan Ocak. Automatic detection of epileptic seizures in eeg using discrete wavelet transform and approximate entropy. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 36(2, Part 1):2027–2036, 2009. ISSN 0957-4174. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2007.12.065>. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0957417407006203>.
- EBM Papst. Produktdatenblatt 4414 hh, 2019. URL <https://asset.conrad.com/media10/add/160267/c1/-/de/001926278DS01/datenblatt-1926278-ebm-papst-4414-hh-axialluefter-24-vdc-280-mh-1-x-b-x-h-119-x-119-x-38-mm.pdf>. Accessed on 16.3.2024.
- F. Pedregosa, G. Varoquaux, A. Gramfort, V. Michel, B. Thirion, O. Grisel, M. Blondel, P. Prettenhofer, R. Weiss, V. Dubourg, J. Vanderplas, A. Passos, D. Cournapeau, M. Brucher, M. Perrot, and E. Duchesnay. Scikit-learn: Machine learning in Python. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 12:2825–2830, 2011.
- Olivier Rioul and Pierre Duhamel. Fast algorithms for discrete and continuous wavelet transforms. *IEEE transactions on information theory*, 38(2):569–586, 1992.
- Graham Upton and Ian Cook. *Understanding statistics*. Oxford University Press, 1996.
- Raphael Vallant. Antropy library, 2018. URL <https://github.com/raphaelvallat/antropy?tab=readme-ov-file>.
- Pauli Virtanen, Ralf Gommers, Travis E. Oliphant, Matt Haberland, Tyler Reddy, David Cournapeau, Evgeni Burovski, Pearu Peterson, Warren Weckesser, Jonathan Bright, Stéfan J. van der Walt, Matthew Brett, Joshua Wilson, K. Jarrod Millman, Nikolay Mayorov, Andrew R. J. Nelson, Eric Jones, Robert Kern, Eric Larson, C J Carey, İlhan Polat, Yu Feng, Eric W. Moore, Jake VanderPlas, Denis Laxalde, Josef Perktold, Robert Cimrman, Ian Henriksen, E. A. Quintero, Charles R. Harris, Anne M. Archibald, Antônio H. Ribeiro, Fabian Pedregosa, Paul van Mulbregt, and SciPy 1.0 Contributors. SciPy 1.0: Fundamental Algorithms for Scientific Computing in Python. *Nature Methods*, 17:261–272, 2020. doi: [10.1038/s41592-019-0686-2](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-019-0686-2).
- Alexander G Volkov. *Plant electrophysiology*. Springer, 2006.
- Petros Xanthopoulos, Panos M. Pardalos, and Theodore B. Trafalis. *Linear Discriminant Analysis*, pages 27–33. Springer New York, New York, NY, 2013. ISBN 978-1-4419-9878-1. doi: [10.1007/978-1-4419-9878-1_4](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-9878-1_4).

Appendix

Single Stimulus

Single channel

Figure 19: Blue single channel

Figure 20: Red single channel

Figure 21: Heat single channel

Figure 22: Wind single channel

Two channels

Figure 23: Blue two channels

Figure 24: Red two channels

Figure 25: Heat two channels

Figure 26: Wind two channels

All channels

Figure 27: Four channels for all stimuli

Increased feature space channels

Figure 28: Blue increased feature space

Figure 29: Red increased feature space

Figure 30: Heat increased feature space

Figure 31: Wind increased feature space

Multiple Stimuli

Figure 32: Blue, Red stimuli

Figure 33: Blue, Red, Heat stimuli

Figure 34: Blue, Red, Heat, Wind stimuli